

Historical Investigation of Nineteenth-Century Migration Patterns of Kabba in Kogi State (1800–1900)

Yalumo, Oluwatoni Faith* and Oghi, Felix E.*

Department of History and Diplomatic Studies, Glorious Vision University, Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author. Email: aoluwatoni@yahoo.com; felix01966@gmail.com

Phone: +2348118611281; +2348060262046

Abstract

This paper investigates the migration patterns of Kabba in present-day Kogi State, Nigeria, between 1800 and 1900, a period marked by Nupe expansion, slave raids, the growth of regional trade, and the early influence of British colonialism. Drawing on Mabogunje's systems approach to migration and Ravenstein's laws of migration, the study examines how push factors such as warfare, tribute demands, and agricultural disruption combined with pull factors including security in fortified settlements, trade opportunities in Lokoja and Bida, and emerging colonial administrative roles to shape patterns of out-migration and in-migration. Using oral histories, archival records, and historical narratives, the analysis demonstrates the existence of dynamic feedback loops: out-migration weakened the rural labour force, while remittances and intermarriages sustained social networks, and the in-migration of Hausa, Ebira, and Yoruba groups transformed local identities. Kabba functioned simultaneously as a place of refuge and a point of exit, revealing both vulnerability and resilience in times of crisis. The study concludes that the interaction of security concerns, economic incentives, and cultural exchange was central to shaping pre-colonial and early colonial mobility in north-central Nigeria, with enduring implications for the region's development and identity.

Keywords: Colonial transition, Migration, Nupe invasions, Push–pull factors, Slave raids

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1. Introduction

One of the major ethnic groups in Kogi State is the Kabba people, also referred to as the Owé. The language of the people is a variant of the Yoruba language known as Owe, which translates as “proverb.” Kabba borders several neighbouring communities such as Abinu, Kiri, Ijumu, Yagba, and Ebira, among others.¹ Kabba belongs to the Western District of Kogi State, Nigeria, where communities are collectively referred to as Okun. These include Kabba, Ijumu, Yagba, Kiri, and Bunu. Their common form of greeting is derived from the word *Okun*, meaning warm greetings.² Kabba is strategically located within a valley surrounded by a series of hills that significantly

influence the lives of the people. It is one of the major ethnic groupings in the state and serves as the headquarters of Kabba-Bunu Local Government Area.³

The Okun people, also known as Okun-Yoruba or the Yoruba-speaking population of Kogi State, share a common ancestry traced to Ile-Ife. They speak a variant of the Yoruba language with slight linguistic differences. The economy of Okunland is primarily based on agriculture, trading, and white-collar employment.⁴ Interaction with the Nupe people in the nineteenth century, particularly during the conquest of Kabba and its environs, brought about significant changes in the lives of the Kabba people. The Hausa also influenced Kabba society through sustained interactions during this period. Similarly, the advent of colonial rule led to substantial transformations in social practices such as marriage, dressing, and housing.⁵

The first major disruption to the traditional life of the Owé occurred during the Nupe incursion of the 1840s. During this period, the socio-political structures, spiritual practices, and daily lives of the people were shaken to their foundations. Nupe rulers imposed their authority and attempted to enforce their ways of life, leading some Owé people to flee into exile due to the harsh conditions. Nupe dominance persisted until their eventual withdrawal following the British incursion in 1895.⁶

Migration refers to the movement of people from one place to another, driven by a complex interaction of economic, social, political, and environmental factors. Individuals and families may migrate in search of better employment opportunities, improved living conditions, educational advancement, or security. Migration has existed throughout human history and has been shaped by personal aspirations, political instability, environmental change, and economic opportunities.

Scholars broadly classify the causes of migration into push and pull factors. Pull factors are conditions that attract people to a particular location, such as economic stability, access to healthcare, security of life and property, and effective governance.⁷ Push factors, on the other hand, compel people to leave their places of origin due to adverse conditions such as insecurity, warfare, poverty, unemployment, poor infrastructure, political discrimination, or environmental degradation.⁸ These historical push and pull forces mirror contemporary migration dynamics, as systemic challenges continue to drive population movement in search of stability and opportunity.

Migration may be voluntary or forced. Voluntary migration is driven by individual choice, often motivated by opportunities for education or employment, while forced migration results from conflict, persecution, or natural disasters. Regardless of its form, migration reflects a fundamental human response to changing circumstances and has played a crucial role in shaping societies and cultures across time and space.

Historically, migration has been a defining feature of human development. Modern humans (*Homo sapiens*) emerged in Africa about 300,000 years ago and began migrating out of the continent between 70,000 and 50,000 years ago, eventually reaching Oceania and Europe.⁹ Religious texts also record instances of migration; for example, Genesis 11:31 documents the movement of Terah, Abram, and their household from Ur of the Chaldeans toward the land of Canaan.¹⁰ These examples underscore migration as a recurring phenomenon driven by survival, opportunity, and divine or social imperatives.

In the case of the Kabba people, migration traces back to Ile-Ife, regarded as

their place of origin. According to historical accounts, Kabba was founded by three hunters from Ile-Ife who settled in the area after prolonged exploration. Subsequent events such as wars, insurrections, Nupe raids, economic pressures, and intermarriage prompted further population movements to and from Kabba.¹¹

Theories of Migration

Renowned Nigerian geographer Akin L. Mabogunje made a significant contribution to migration studies through his *Systems Approach to a Theory of Rural–Urban Migration*, which provides a framework for understanding migration as a dynamic process shaped by interacting social, economic, political, and environmental forces.¹²

Mabogunje's systems approach views migration as part of a broader societal system, characterised by feedback mechanisms that influence both areas of origin and destination. Although developed in the context of post-colonial Africa, this framework is applicable to nineteenth-century Kabba. During the period 1800–1900, migration was driven by push factors such as Nupe slave raids and warfare, and pull factors including security and trade opportunities in centres such as Bida and Lokoja. These forces transformed Kabba's societal system under Yoruba expansion, Nupe domination, and early British influence.

Nupe-Fulani incursions disrupted agriculture through tribute demands and displacement, while the establishment of Lokoja as a trading post in 1860 attracted migrants seeking economic opportunities. Environmental factors, including fertile land and riverine access, initially supported settlement but later exposed communities to raids. Feedback mechanisms emerged as out-migration reduced rural labour, undermined agriculture, and increased dependency on urban centres, while remittances and kinship networks sustained Kabba's resilience.

Adaptation, a key component of Mabogunje's theory, is evident in Kabba's experience. Displaced Kabba people in Bida became labourers or tributaries within emirate hierarchies while retaining cultural markers such as the Owe dialect. In-migrants such as Ebira and Bassa-Nge contributed skills in weaving and trade, fostering cultural exchange but also generating competition over resources. By the late nineteenth century, British economic activities under the Royal Niger Company drew migrants to Lokoja, reshaping attitudes toward wage labour and colonial economies.

Overall, migration functioned as both a survival strategy and a source of structural imbalance in Kabba. While it enabled population redistribution and resilience during crises, it also led to rural depopulation and cultural disruption. Mabogunje's systems approach thus highlights migration as a transformative force in Kabba's social, economic, and cultural history during a period of profound change.

2. Ravenstein's Laws of Migration

Migration, as a fundamental aspect of human behaviour, has long attracted scholarly attention, with researchers seeking to explain the patterns, causes, and consequences of human mobility. One of the earliest and most influential theoretical contributions to migration studies was made by Ernst Georg Ravenstein through his formulation of the *Laws of Migration* (1885; 1889).¹³

Ravenstein's laws, developed in the late nineteenth century, identify key regularities in migration behaviour. He argued that most migrants move short distances, while long-distance migrants are more likely to be drawn toward major economic and administrative centres. Migration, according to Ravenstein, often occurs in stages: individuals first move from rural areas to nearby towns before eventually relocating to larger cities. Urban centres grow primarily through migration rather than natural population increase, as cities exert a strong pull through economic opportunities, while rural areas generate push forces such as poverty and limited livelihood options.¹⁴

Ravenstein also observed distinct demographic patterns in migration. He noted that young adults, particularly those between the ages of 20 and 35, constitute the majority of migrants. Gender differences were also emphasized: women were more likely to engage in short-distance migration, often linked to marriage, while men tended to migrate over longer distances in search of employment. Furthermore, Ravenstein introduced the concept of *counter-streams*, arguing that every major migration flow generates a smaller reverse movement of return migrants. Central to his analysis was the assertion that economic considerations—especially the search for better living conditions and employment—were the dominant motivations for migration, facilitated by improvements in transportation such as railways.¹⁵

When applied to Kabba, Ravenstein's economic emphasis complements Mabogunje's systems approach. While Mabogunje incorporates social, economic, and environmental variables within a dynamic feedback system, Ravenstein places primary emphasis on economic motives and the gradual, staged nature of migration. In the Kabba context, both theories help explain the patterns of population movement observed during the nineteenth century.

Social factors, particularly intermarriage, played a crucial role in Kabba's migration history. Indigenous Kabba women frequently married into neighbouring communities, creating social networks that sustained continuous migration flows. These kinship ties encouraged both out-migration and return movements, reinforcing Ravenstein's notion of counter-streams while also fitting within Mabogunje's feedback mechanisms.

Economic motivations, as highlighted by Ravenstein, are evident in Kabba's extensive trading activities. Kabba's strategic location at the crossroads of several communities enabled its people to engage in regional commerce with areas such as Owo, Ekiti, Ilorin, Ibadan, and Benue. Trade in agricultural produce, including cotton, woven cloths, and yams, often required traders to remain away from Kabba for extended periods. In some cases, traders settled permanently in neighbouring communities, returning home mainly during festive occasions.¹⁶ These movements reflect long-distance, economically motivated migration consistent with Ravenstein's laws.

Environmental factors, emphasized more strongly by Mabogunje, were equally significant in Kabba's migration experience. Persistent insecurity caused by slave raids and Nupe invasions rendered the environment unsafe, forcing many inhabitants to flee in search of security.¹⁷ Between 1800 and 1900, the collapse of the Oyo Empire and the rise of the Sokoto Caliphate destabilised the region, compelling many Kabba people to migrate southward for safety.¹⁸ These displacements intensified during

periods of Fulani jihadist incursions and Nupe slave expeditions.¹⁹

Economic disruption further accelerated migration. The breakdown of traditional trade routes and agricultural systems forced many Kabba residents to seek better opportunities in neighbouring communities.²⁰ British colonial activities in the late nineteenth century, including military expeditions and demands for forced labour, compounded these pressures and contributed to further displacement.²¹

Conversely, Kabba also experienced significant in-migration during this period. Relative stability in certain phases made Kabba a refuge for displaced populations from the former Oyo Empire and surrounding regions.²² Its location along revived trade routes attracted Hausa traders and other commercial groups.²³ Missionary activities and colonial administration introduced new pull factors, including schools, medical facilities, and employment opportunities. The designation of Kabba as a provincial headquarters in 1900 further enhanced its appeal to migrants seeking security and opportunity.^{24,25}

These population movements profoundly reshaped Kabba's social and cultural landscape. The influx of Yoruba, Hausa, Igala, and other groups produced a complex demographic mix that redefined local identities.²⁶ Although competition over resources occasionally generated tension, the overall trend was toward cultural integration and the emergence of a distinct regional identity.²⁷ By the close of the nineteenth century, these migration patterns had repositioned Kabba within Nigeria's evolving political framework and laid the foundation for colonial administrative structures whose effects remain visible in contemporary debates on identity and development.^{28,29}

3. The Nupe Invasion and Migration in Kabba

Kabba was among the African communities profoundly affected by the transatlantic slave trade and its lingering consequences. Even after the formal abolition of the trade in the early nineteenth century, its legacy continued to shape local dynamics. Between 1800 and 1900, migration patterns in Kabba were strongly influenced by internal conflicts, Nupe expansion, and colonial penetration.³⁰

The Nupe conquests were a major driver of migration during this period. As a dominant regional power, the Nupe expanded into Okunland, including Kabba, through sustained military campaigns. These incursions resulted in mass displacement, depopulation, and the establishment of new settlements.³¹ Under rulers such as Usman Zaki and Masaba, repeated raids forced many inhabitants to flee or face enslavement.³²

Nupe domination disrupted indigenous political structures and imposed a tribute-based administrative system known as the *Ogba* system. Through this framework, conquered territories were governed indirectly by Nupe-appointed officials, and annual tributes were extracted to sustain the Bida Emirate. Kabba became a vassal state, enjoying limited peace but suffering hostility from neighbouring communities.³³ Conflicts such as the Ogun Igberi war were particularly destructive, compelling Kabba to accept punitive tribute agreements after widespread devastation.³⁴ During Masaba's reign, attacks intensified, with settlements such as Egbe serving as military bases for further incursions.³⁵

The demographic consequences were severe. Nupe military campaigns between

1800 and 1860 are estimated to have displaced or captured thousands of Kabba inhabitants, many of whom were sold into trans-Saharan slave networks or relocated to Nupe urban centres. Defensive migrations to hilltop fortifications and forest refuges became common survival strategies.^{36,37}

Colonial rule and shifting economic priorities further influenced migration patterns. British administrative reorganisation and infrastructure development, including road networks linking Kabba to Lokoja, facilitated increased mobility. The transition toward commodity export economies generated new labour demands and reshaped migration flows well into the early twentieth century.^{38,39,40}

Social factors such as intermarriage also promoted voluntary migration, particularly among women who relocated to join spouses in neighbouring communities. Cultural ties with other Yoruba-speaking regions further encouraged movement and integration.⁴¹ Environmental pressures, including land scarcity and possible climatic stress, likely contributed to migration toward more fertile regions, even though specific records remain limited.⁴²

4. Conclusion

From the foregoing discussion, it is evident that migration in Kabba between 1800 and 1900 was shaped by a complex interplay of socio-political, economic, and environmental forces. Economic opportunities linked to regional trade and colonial restructuring played a major role, while insecurity arising from Nupe invasions and broader political instability generated strong push factors. Social networks, especially those created through marriage and kinship, sustained both voluntary and forced migration.

The nineteenth-century migration experience of Kabba reflects a broader narrative of adaptation and resilience in the face of profound transformation. Colonial policies, economic ambitions, social relations, and environmental pressures collectively influenced population movements. Understanding these dynamics is essential for appreciating the historical complexity of migration in Nigeria and the enduring impact of these movements on contemporary cultural, political, and developmental realities.

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